

Evaluating Abortion Care Quality in a California State University Student Health Center

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Background

- In the U.S., 2.8 billion unintended pregnancies occur annually and about half (40%) will result in an abortion
- Rates of abortion are highest in women ages 18-24, corresponding to college years
- MAB is the most common form of abortion
- 93-98% effective up to 77 days' gestation

Problem Statement

- The college SHC where this project took place just recently started providing MAB services, per the SB 24 mandate
- MAB is a brand-new service and limited information exists to evaluate the degree it improves patient and practice outcomes
- There is no current method of evaluation that assesses quality of abortion care at SHC

Purpose Statement

- The purpose of this project was to conduct a program evaluation of MAB services at SHC
- Specific aims of this project were to:

1. Establish a baseline understanding of the target population
2. Identify areas of improvement
3. Improve patient and practice outcomes related to abortion care

Abortion Stigma: Common Theme

Patient Barriers

- cost
- travel
- schedule
- stigma*
- religiosity
- shame

Provider Barriers

- religiosity
- stigma*
- lack of empathy
- judgment
- insensitivity
- criminal liability

Abortion Quality Metrics

- lack of standardization
- restrictive nature
- lack of follow-up
- underreporting of abortion incidence
- scarcity of data
- stigma*

Senate Bill 24 (SB 24): The College Student Right to Access Act

California is the first state to ever require college student health centers (SHCs) to provide medication abortion (MAB) services on college campuses

Theoretical Framework

Results: Review of Electronic Health Records (EHR)

Results: Patient Satisfaction Survey

The patient who participated in the patient satisfaction survey rated that her MAB visit "went well" and the overall care was "good." The patient appreciated the use of "handouts" and reports that the staff treated her with respect. Pain management was also "somewhat effective."

Methods

- **Setting:** College SHC in Los Angeles County
- **Design:** Program evaluation using a mixed-methods project design
- **Participants:** DNP Student, SHC Director and Assistant Director, Clinical Patient Health Educator, Senior Health Promotion Specialist, Information Technologists
- **Ethical Considerations:**
 - ✓ IRB approval from CSUF and CSUN
 - ✓ Letter of support
 - ✓ De-identified data collection and analysis

Limitations

- Small sample size
- SB 24 is very recent legislation and MAB is a brand-new service to college SHCs in CA
- Limited patient satisfaction survey timeframe contributed to low turnout and eligibility

Conclusion

- MAB workflow at SHC is successful
- All MABs were complete and no hospitalized adverse events reported
- No unnecessary wait times in clinic
- SB 24 significantly reduced financial burden of pregnant college women who wanted an abortion

Recommendations

- Incorporate culturally-tailored interventions for the international students who interact with the SHC for MAB services
- Quality improvement to focus MAB education and contraceptive decision making
- Comprehensive pain management counseling
- Continue PDSA cycles based on study findings

References

